

**Rapid Detection and control system for Antimicrobial
Resistance**
Public Procurement of Innovation

**Recommendations to boost the potential
of Public Procurement of Innovation to
tackle Antimicrobial Resistance through
a One Health approach**

Co-funded by the
COSME programme
of the European Union

Introduction

RaDAR-PPI is a European Commission co-funded project which addresses the European urgent need of a rapid detection and effective infection control system for antimicrobial resistance (AMR) through the implementation of a value-based, cross-border collaborative public procurement of innovation (PPI). It started on January 2022 and finishes on June 2026.

After the identification of common clinical needs by a cross-border group of five healthcare organizations from Spain, France and Italy, followed by an open market consultation with suppliers and tendering process, a series of innovative AMR diagnostic solutions and clinical decision support systems were procured through a value-based procurement approach. These solutions have been implemented and holistically evaluated across different healthcare settings, aiming to improve sample, pathogen, patient, and prescription management. By reducing the time to diagnosis, providing more targeted antibiotic treatments and supporting more rational use of antibiotics, the solutions contribute to tackling AMR.

For more detailed information on RaDAR-PPI, you can visit the website [here](#).

In addition, RaDAR-PPI's Inserm team, which coordinate the second edition of the [European Joint Action on Antimicrobial Resistance and Healthcare-Associated Infections \(EU-JAMRAI-2\)](#) and the [French Professional Community Network on Antimicrobial Resistance \(PROMISE\)](#), has produced a deliverable exploring several areas of action to boost the potential of PPI to tackle AMR through a One Health approach. For more detailed information, the full deliverable is available [here](#).

Within the communication framework of the RaDAR-PPI project, **two animated videoseries** were made to disseminate and raise awareness on [AMR](#) (in collaboration with [EU-JAMRAI-2](#)) and [PPI](#).

This policy brief summarises the main challenges identified when reviewing the One Health scope of EU regulations on health and innovation with potential AMR relevance, as well as the analysis of PPI practices on AMR by EU institutions and RADAR-PPI participating countries. It also provides general recommendations to promote the uptake of PPI to tackle AMR across One Health sectors.

1. Review of EU health and innovation regulations with potential AMR relevance and One Health scope

Most of the regulations identified are either under review or have been created or enhanced just recently due to the EU innovation agenda aiming to boost innovation and competitiveness. The regulations most clearly impacting on AMR focus mainly on the human sector, including:

- The **EU pharma legislation revision**, which creates pull incentives for the development of and access to new and existing antimicrobials;
- The **Critical Medicine Alliance**, which aims to improve the availability, supply and production of critical medicines, such as antimicrobials;
- The **AMR actions by DG HERA**, such as using innovation procurement for developing AMR diagnostics, joint cross-border procurement of new antibiotics or the launch of HERA Invest, a €100 million guarantee to support investments in innovative technologies to tackle priority health threats.

Other newly implemented or proposed regulations with AMR scope involving the animal or the environment are:

- The **Veterinary Medicinal Products Regulation**, which updates the rules on the authorisation and use of veterinary medicines in the EU, stimulates the development of innovative veterinary medicines for small markets, and provides with medicine monitoring databases;
- The **recast Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive**, which contemplates surveillance and advanced quaternary treatment of AMR in wastewater by Member States financed through a polluter-pays principle by the sectors responsible for the pollution, starting from 2028.

Challenges

- **Limited cross-pollination across public health actors and regulations:**

While the new EU innovation agenda attempts to modernize, simplify and accelerate the competitiveness of the EU, the EU health regulatory landscape is highly complex and difficult to navigate. As a consequence, scientists and public health officials need to regularly conduct large studies reviewing EU and country regulations. Despite the existence of communication fora like the EU Health Policy Platform, the European Health Forum Gastein or the AMR One Health Platform, there is still limited cross-talk among public health initiatives and actors even within one same One Health sector, preventing the alignment of potentially related health policies since early stages of their design.

For example, the Innovation Procurement and the Health Technology Assessment (HTA) regulations, which have been progressing separately, share several areas of common interest when performing medical, social, economic and ethical assessments or horizon scanning of newly emerging health technologies of added value for the health systems. In this regard, the London Office of Health Economics have published the STRIDES (Spectrum, Transmission, Research, Insurance, Diversity, Enablement and Surveillance) and STEDI (Spectrum, Transmission, Enablement, Diversity, and Insurance) frameworks to address the scope limitations of existing HTA regulations and reimbursement frameworks, which fail to capture the full value of AMR diagnostics and antimicrobials.

- **Lack of One Health regulatory framework:**

Despite multiple high-level declarations on One Health governance, such as the Quadripartite's One Health Joint Plan of Action, the One Health Governance report by the Scientific Advice Mechanism or the Cross-agency One Health task force, there is still a lack of clear coordination on many EU policies across One Health sectors, especially for one health issues like AMR and other pollutants of emerging concern, which may potentially lead to silos, redundancies and areas of legal uncertainty. As a matter of fact, the animal and environmental sectors are lagging behind in terms of health policy inclusion within priority national action plans, having to compete for funding schemes usually prioritized for the human sector, and turning into a slowdown on innovation for One Health challenges.

With the exception of the development, stockpiling and procurement strategies of antimicrobials in the human sector, there is limited AMR prioritization across research, development and innovation policies in the animal and environmental sectors, especially for vaccines, diagnostics, waste management tools and alternatives to antimicrobials.

- **Lack of green public procurement (GPP) criteria for pharmaceuticals and diagnostics as well as verification procedures and indicators of environmental compliance:**

While the European Commission has been developing voluntary and minimum mandatory GPP criteria for several product groups, at this moment in the EU, GPP criteria for medical devices are voluntary, outdated and under revision. Existing requirements focus mainly on high-energy consumption devices, leaving laboratory and *in vitro* diagnostics out of scope. In addition, no medical device regulation nor GPP criteria exist at EU level for animal health diagnostics, which creates legal uncertainty towards the certification of performance, validity, safety, and environmental aspects for their procurement.

Regarding medicines, no specific product group within the GPP framework exists for pharmaceuticals. In the field of antimicrobial procurement, the Nordic countries are the ones taking the lead at EU level in the application of GPP criteria, for example by requesting the location of the manufacturer, the formulation of active pharmaceutical substances or data on the concentration of drugs in waterways, for which lack of transparency is common across globalised supply chains operating under alternative environmental regulatory systems. As a consequence, Member States establish country-specific GPP requirements, which creates more barriers for companies, especially SME, wishing to apply for tenders in multiple countries.

Concerning verification procedures of environmental compliance for the procurement of medicines, currently these are mainly based on tenderer self-declarations without the requirement for third-party verification. In support of the verification, the applicability of **ecolabels and certifications** should be further considered as acceptable proof. However, there is a current **lack of ecolabelling schemes applicable to wastewater treatment**.

The AMR Industry Alliance, a group of international manufacturers of antibiotics and other pharmaceuticals, together with the **British Standards Institute (BSI)**, have developed a new global Minimized Risk of AMR certification to promote and demonstrate **responsible antibiotic manufacturing in the global pharmaceutical supply chain**. At this moment, however, this certification system is not applied neither in municipal WWTPs nor in hospital settings to verify compliance with environmental standards on polluting emissions.

In addition, within the framework of the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, the European Commission is proposing the **Extended Producer Responsibility Scheme** for manufacturers of medicinal and cosmetic products to cover at least 80% of the costs of removing micro-pollutants from urban wastewater. However, the pharmaceutical industry has expressed concerns on the potential impact of this scheme on the availability, affordability and security of supply of medicines.

- **Lack of innovation benchmarking and harmonization of indicators across countries and One Health sectors for AMR**

While there is EU-level benchmarking of national policy frameworks and national investments on innovation procurement as well as GPP policies across Member States and their regions, this benchmarking is, as of now, rather general and does not look into sector-specific areas of innovation needs, such as AMR or orphan medicines. In this regard, specific AMR innovation indicators across One Health sectors need to be proposed and agreed upon for national and European innovation monitoring frameworks so that policy actions can be derived from it and improve innovation uptake for new antimicrobials (particularly antibiotics), vaccines, diagnostics, waste management tools and safe and effective alternatives to antimicrobials.

Recommendations

- Cross-collaboration, communication and exchange platforms, in addition to observership and secondment programmes, across public health initiatives and One Health sectors should be developed and enhanced at EU and country level. This would help the inclusion of public health officials from various sectors and public health areas in relevant health policy discussions, avoid siloed legislation and support the development and implementation of a One Health regulatory framework, with a stronger emphasis on the animal and environment sectors.
- In order to promote the uptake of mandatory GPP environmental criteria for pharmaceuticals, verification procedures of environmental compliance, such as third-party certification methods of discharge targets should be developed, harmonised and applied by pharmaceutical industry and procurement agencies. This would contribute to reducing antibiotic concentrations in the environment and ensure environmental quality compliance across wastewater treatment plants, hospital settings, and manufacturers.
- These GPP criteria and verification procedures of environmental compliance should also be developed and harmonised for both human and animal health diagnostics, including laboratory, *in vitro*, point-of-care (PoC) and on-farm devices. This should aim to reduce unnecessary plastic use, carbon emissions and rare material usage from distant countries and incentive the development of local and biodegradable materials.
- Regarding the application of the Extended Producer Responsibility scheme, government authorities and industry should work closely together to find new financial incentives, environmentally-friendly and cost-effective wastewater treatment methods and alternative substances with greener profiles.
- After their benchmarking review across countries, regions and sectors, it is crucial to analyse the impact of implementing GPP national policies towards reaching sustainability goals with a view to drive policy action and address barriers and gaps.

2. Review of PPI practices on AMR by EU institutions and RADAR participating countries

- **EU Public Procurement Data for policy action: need for more data sharing, transparency, integration and interoperability across countries, regions, and sectors, as well as standardisation of PPI definitions and systematic labelling**

As of today, the European public procurement data space remains difficult to navigate for policy makers and citizens looking for information on public spending, as well as for companies wishing to apply for tenders in several countries. For instance, national authorities are only obliged to publish public procurement data above specific EU thresholds, resulting in an underrepresented repository of procurement data at European level and hindering the assessment and exploitation of meaningful data on public spending for policy action.

As a consequence, public and private-driven initiatives are carrying out secondary use and analysis based on official procurement data sources not readily available, causing substantial data fragmentation and government distrust. The recent **Public Procurement Data Space (PPDS)**, launched in 2024 with the aim to connect European and national procurement databases, represents an important step forward. However, as of now, it is not mandatory for Member States to participate, therefore its full potential might be underutilised.

The review of procurement practices on AMR at country level showed a clear lack of procurement data transparency, availability, (re)usability and integration across countries and sectors, especially in regionalised countries with strong administrative borders. While national or regional procurement portals generally allow for specific data consultations using Common Procurement Vocabulary (CPV) values or keywords, big data extraction and analysis, however, still require highly specialised IT and language programming expertise, which is much beyond EU citizens' average digital skills. This was evidenced by the challenges encountered for Spain and Italy, where a retrospective analysis of AMR procurement practices was not possible within this project.

Moreover, if the intention is to benchmark innovation procurement practices, only a certain number of Member States and regions are explicitly labelling these practices as 'innovation procurement' in their data portals. This makes it difficult to identify PPI activities and to evaluate their impact.

- **Review of procurement practices on AMR: underutilization of PPI and PCP at European level, especially for animal and environmental health**

The review of PPI practices at EU institutional and national level showed a clear underutilization of public procurement as a tool to bring forward AMR innovation, with a special emphasis on the animal and environmental sectors to tackle AMR from a One Health perspective.

At EU institutional level, most of the procurement practices on AMR identified were outsourced services on research consultancy, training, capacity building and dissemination. The most innovative procurements were carried out by DG HERA, such as pre-commercial procurements (PCPs) on rapid PoC antimicrobial susceptibility testing and metagenomic sequencing diagnostics, a pull incentive pilot for joint procurement on new antibiotics, in addition to ECDC's procurements on whole genomic sequencing services for epidemiology and surveillance of resistant bacteria.

At national level, no PPI or PCP initiatives on AMR diagnostics and therapeutics were found in France. Public procurement was mostly used for the provision of automated diagnostic systems, followed by anti-infectious therapies, mass spectrometry, DNA sequencing, molecular biology systems, rapid diagnostic tests, and vaccine in the human clinical setting and with a low level of innovation. Although of a comparatively lower volume, public procurement of information management services focused mainly on vaccination campaign and nosocomial infection monitoring platforms.

It is important to highlight that specific European funding calls have enabled the development of strategic procurement initiatives in AMR. In particular, the Catalan health system has followed a strategy to engage in EU-funded innovation procurement instruments, starting with participation in the open call H2020-ICT-2015 "Pre-commercial procurement open to all areas of public interest requiring new ICT solutions". This led to the ANTI-SUPERBUGS PCP project, co-financed at 70%, aimed at advancing innovative solutions for AMR. From this experience, it was decided to participate in the COSME programme call "Co-financing of public procurement of innovation consortia COS-PPI-2020-2-04", under which the RaDAR-PPI project was funded and implemented. This progression illustrates how EU calls can support a structured pathway from PCP to PPI and shows that procurement has been used in Europe as a strategic instrument to address AMR challenges.

Recommendations

- PPI should be included and prioritised in National and European Action Plans in order to boost innovation and competitiveness, in particular for the current AMR challenges across One Health sectors
- Public procurement data sharing, transparency, integration and interoperability across One Health sectors, countries and their regions, as well as standardisation and labelling of PPI practices, is crucial in order to ensure its full exploitation to drive policy action. This should be done within the framework of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and TRUST (Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability, and Technology) Principles
- Existing EU-level innovation benchmarking mechanisms should be used to monitor PPI practices with harmonised indicators tailored to AMR innovation needs across One Health sectors, countries and regions. This would help assess the impact and optimise national and European innovation strategies, ideally through the application of SMART criteria (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Timely) and Progressive Management Pathway (PMP) frameworks.
- Cross-action between EU funding programmes should be strengthened to ensure continuity between PCP and PPI. The RaDAR-PPI experience (building on the AntiSuperbugs PCP and progressing to the RaDAR-PPI) validates cross-DG coordination as a model for impact-driven funding.
- There is a need for dedicated strategic scaling instruments to support the uptake and expansion of innovations beyond initial project funding. This includes the development of large-scale, longer-term PPI projects to enable adoption and system-wide impact.

Strategic recommendations for successful value-based tender design and PPI adoption and sustainability:

During the RaDAR-PPI project, a **Value-Based Cross-Border Collaborative PPI Handbook** was developed. Its main recommendation is the application of a structured methodology to PPI to ensure it acts as a lever for systemic transformation. Based on this handbook, the following key recommendations can be extracted:

- **Application and further development of the "Permeability to Value" Methodology:** This framework ensures that the procurement procedure remains open to the needs and desired outcomes of all stakeholders (patients, professionals, providers, health systems, and society) throughout its lifecycle. It also supports the transition from price-based approaches to value- and outcome-based procurement.
- **Utilization of the Theory of Change:** Policy actors should use this framework to reverse-engineer procurement goals, starting from long-term impacts and outcomes to define short-term activities and technical requirements. This provides a clear roadmap for adapting innovations to local contexts and ensuring value is preserved from design to implementation.
- **Requirement for Robust Business Cases:** Future instruments should mandate a well-defined economic baseline. If prior analysis is absent, an updated baseline is critical to measure the impact of innovative interventions.
- **Alignment of procurement models with innovation maturity:** Procurement models should reflect the readiness of the solutions (from R&D to deployment) and include flexible, value-based and risk-sharing mechanisms, enabling evidence generation while supporting innovation uptake.
- **Embedding evaluation and evidence generation:** Evaluation should be integrated throughout the procurement lifecycle, including the definition of clear key performance indicators (KPIs), data collection systems and continuous monitoring, to assess clinical, economic, and system impact and support scaling.
- **Promotion of coordinated and cross-border procurement approaches:** Collaborative procurement models should be encouraged, as they allow local needs to be addressed within specific contexts while enabling joint, scalable solutions to shared challenges. The adoption of coordinated cross-border procurement strengthens efficiency, facilitates knowledge sharing, and enhances the capacity of public buyers to generate system-wide impact.

Lessons learned from RADAR-PPI for successful operationalisation of AMR diagnostic innovation

Apart from technological performance or procurement mechanisms, the RaDAR-PPI experience shows that, from a clinical-site perspective (including hospitals and primary care), the successful integration of AMR-related innovations into existing clinical workflows is crucial. Key challenges include aligning nursing, clinical, and laboratory schedules, managing operational constraints in sample processing, and ensuring a well-structured pre-analytical, analytical and post-analytical process. Addressing these factors is essential to ensure effective and sustainable implementation in real healthcare settings.

Workflow design, training, and early involvement of end-users are critical success factors. Clinical pathways must be co-defined with healthcare professionals to ensure that innovations are usable and fully integrated into routine practice. In addition, hands-on training and gradual implementation approaches can significantly improve user adoption.

It is also imperative to strengthen the link between rapid diagnostic capabilities and their direct impact on clinical decision-making. Early detection enables faster implementation of key actions such as patient isolation, de-isolation, and optimisation of antimicrobial therapy. These actions have a direct effect on patient management, infection control, and resource utilisation, and should be more explicitly highlighted as part of the clinical value proposition.

In order to assess the clinical, social, economic and ethical impact of these innovation strategies and optimize the clinical management of hospital infections and colonizations, a cost-benefit analysis comparing the microbiological, clinical, hospital and economic data of the standard-of-care workflow vs the applied clinical intervention after the change of management should be performed.

For this purpose, it is of utmost importance to enable hospital data integration policies and identify KPIs across healthcare systems through the involvement of various hospital stakeholders, such as infectiologists, microbiologists, nurses, IT, administration and legal staff, in addition to other decision-makers and payers, with a view to be recognized and included in health action plans and generate value for patients, health systems, and society.

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Published:

June 2026

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**With the collaboration of
partners of the RADAR-PPI
consortium**

This project has received funding from the COSME Programme of the European Union (Grant Agreement N° 101036228 under the Call for Proposal “Co-financing of public procurement of innovation consortia COS-PPI-2020-2-04”)

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